

How Green Technology can Affect Organizational Process: IKEA's Green Products

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Abstract:-Green technology refers to a type of technology that is considered environmentally friendly based on their production process of the supply chain. Green tech - an acronym for "raw technology" - could also refer to the production of clean energy, the use of alternative fuels, and less harmful technologies in the environment than fossil fuels. Green technology ensures the minimum effect of humans on nature.

This study will analyze how important is sustainable development and how important is the use of Green Products, through which we assess the buying behavior of the people. We are going see how Organization like IKEA are making their products, whether it is going to support the sustainable development. It may be helpful to recommend structural changes when the organization considers green technology.

Keywords:- Green technology, IKEA, sustainable development, supply chain.

I. INTRODUCTION

The title for this task is. Green technology is the development and properly using of tools, systems and products used to save the environment and resources that reduce and reduce the negative impact of human activities. As an organization the vision of IKEA is to create a better daily life for all, by offering a variety of products at such low prices that as many people as possible can afford it. IKEA's focus on the better success and longevity of their unique heart culture that incorporates enthusiasm, togetherness, and the power to unite people while helping them to feel community through the help of colleagues who share their culture. IKEA focuses on work equity with a cohesive, open, and caring management style that provides a happy work environment, job security and a caring attitude of people who are encouraged to take action, express their ideas and commit themselves.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. The Importance of Green Technologies and Energy Efficiency for Environmental Protection

Environmental protection, resource conservation and addressing other social and economic factors for sustainable development are essential. Green efforts approved for resource conservation, and environmental protection will help conserve the high level of economic growth required to meet the basic needs satisfactorily quality of life in the future. Sustainable development that respects social equity and environmental health is possible it only happens when it

gains strong international awareness and major changes trends in the production and use of patterns. To move forward in sustainable development, policymakers must consider not only local economic concerns, but also major scientific and technological challenges affecting all countries. [1]

B. Green Technology Foresight about environmentally friendly products and materials

The foundation needed for agriculture to thrive in the environment A friendly guideline is that research is done about nature technologies and methods and how they can be used. There is a need a priority research effort focused on those related issues reducing environmental problems affecting agricultural production negative impact on the environment, improving animal welfare and new discoveries agricultural methods and products. [2]

C. Advantages and Disadvantages of Green Technology; Goals, Challenges and Strengths

Green technology products are included in the R&D category. Products are reclassified to use less hazardous materials, require less transportation, operate less efficiently, and promote end-of-life recycling. So, in terms of environmental sustainability, the technology industry is embracing change. They change to avoid side effects or to meet the green demand or to achieve both.[3]

D. IKEA AND THE NATURAL STEP

At IKEA we will always strive to minimize any environmental impacts that may be the result of our work. [Policy] will require our concerted efforts and will require implementation, innovation, and unconventional solutions. In many ways the IKEA environmental program were present in its core operational processes. Flat packaging and chlorine-free paper used in their catalogs and advertising flyers were two examples taken directly from the company's savings and shipping. Can be understood as a natural extension of business culture as resource conservation features [4]

E. Eco-efficiency for sustainability: IKEA's environmental policy in Russia

We look at environmental efficiency as part of sustainability to develop and analyze its various meanings. According to the WBCSD "eco efficiency is achieved through the delivery of competitive value and services that meet the needs of the people and bring quality of life while gradually declining the environmental impacts and resources of resources throughout the life cycle to at least a linear level with a fixed load capacity of the earth" (WBCSD, 2000), i.e., creating a relatively small amount impact on the

environment. To calculate environmental efficiency the formula proposed by WBCSD was used.[5]

F. Sustainability Strategies in IKEA with the focus on Production and Suppliers

This activity tries to give you another idea of how the annual reports are viewed that companies present themselves to their customers and stakeholders. Plus, it tries to show how they present their sustainability strategies to make it clear that other pages can have a slightly changing background for the purpose of not just presenting the best side of the company IKEA but also to assure the reader that they do well, and people should buy their products.[6]

G. Green Technology: A veritable Tool for Achieving Technological Transformation and Diversification of the Nation's Economy

Greenness is about the knowledge-based use of God's physical gift of nature to further our preservation using technology and processes that are friendly to the environment. The environment reacts to human ignorance which in turn leads to uncontrollable processes that often quickly change our way of life.[7]

H. IKEA's organizational culture and rewards-management

Case studies have shown that IKEA has rich and unique cultural pillars, rewards and motivational management built to achieve and maintain greater success and better performance while caring for people and the planet. However, IKEA has faced various challenges around the world related to the enforcement of their culture; controlling cultural diversity; and maintaining quality awards and promotional policies and programs.[8]

I. IKEA company analysis Research Paper

The company wraps up its products with environmentally friendly materials. According to its policy statement, the company strives to produce high quality products at low prices. It aims to reduce production costs and gain competitive advantage through cost effectiveness and improved value chain. It plays an important role in the corporate social responsibility. It works with Non-Governmental Organizations to protect the lives of its clients. The company uses a variety of marketing strategies. In the marketing mix, it sells its products at a lower price, attracting more customers. [9]

III.IMPORTANCE OF GREEN TECHNOLOGY

Green technology is an environmentally friendly technology that is being developed to be used in an environmentally friendly manner and to protect natural resources. The importance of green technology cannot be overemphasized especially in the context of humanity. Besides, being green is the only way to help mankind emerge from the current crisis. Therefore, before things get worse, it is important to realize the importance of raw technology to solve problems.

IV.TARGET THROUGH GREEN TECHNOLOGY

The goal of green technology is to meet the needs of the community in ways that do not harm or deplete the world's natural resources. Moreover, the idea is to meet current needs without making any compromises. Besides, it is necessary to find a destination to find out all about the purposes of this type of technology. The focus of raw technology is to make products that can be fully recovered or reused. In addition, steps are being taken to reduce waste and pollution as one of the most important objectives of green technology by changing production and consumption patterns. In addition, it is necessary to develop other technologies to prevent any further damage to the environment and health. The solution is rain on the use of this type of technology to benefit and protect the planet. The key objectives of green technology are to deliver sustainable livelihoods, improve renewable energy, reduce waste production, save energy resources, build more recyclable and renewable products, and establish alternatives to processes that affect people and the environment.

V. GREEN MARKETING: IKEA 'S PRODUCTS

The basic belief of IKEA as a company is that consumers should not choose between stylish designs, affordable prices, and sustainability when purchasing their products. The company uses its online content to encourage customers to live an environmentally responsible life.

They also lead by example eco-friendly practices that include having solar panels in 90 percent of their buildings in the United States and reducing waste disposal at landfills. IKEA reaped many marketing rewards through their green efforts by embracing their core purpose in everything they do. As they point out, if you are going to use purpose-driven ecommerce content to benefit as a product, it is important to clearly show how you are embracing your purpose.

VI.IKEA'S SUSTAINABLE SUPPLY CHAIN LEADERSHIP

IKEA Group has demonstrated its strong leadership by continuing to expand its commitment which includes the field of sustainable planning of the supply chain. IKEA is investing more than \$ 1.1 billion to create a sustainable supply chain that includes forests, recycling, renewable energy, and biomaterials. This is not just good in the world it is a smart business as these investments reduce risk and stabilize costs. The continuous supply chain minimizes the effects of shock, prevents disruption, and ensures long-term access to objects. As a public symbol the IKEA's sustainable position also contributes to the segregation that offers the benefits of reputation.

The company is also developing alternative packaging methods that include a completely rotting variety made of mushrooms. Mycelium "fungus packaging" is produced by Evocative and its packaging is part of IKEA's comprehensive waste disposal program and enhances recycling.

VII. HYPOTHESIS

- H0 - Green technology products cannot help in achieving sustainable development in future.
- H1 – Green technology products can help in achieving sustainable development in future.
- H0 – IKEA’S products are not environmentally friendly.
- H1 – IKEAS’S products are environment friendly.
- H0 – Customers are not satisfied with the IKEA’S green products.
- H1– Customers are satisfied with the IKEA’S green products.

VIII. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In this Research, the data has been taken from two sources i.e., the primary and secondary sources. The primary source of data has been taken as a Questionnaire and secondary source of data has been taken from books, journals, articles, Ikea ‘s website, various author’s articles.

We are trying to interpret the data that how feasible the Ikea’s products in achieving the sustainable development. We are going to collect the data of 50 people as a primary survey, from there we are going to interpret the data and then we can draw the conclusion.

Fig 1

The above-mentioned graph gives detailed explanation of Hypothesis **“How Green Technology can help in achieving sustainable development in future”**. We raised a questionnaire which have the data, that people believe in sustainability, green products are the products which can help in achieving that sustainability.

IKEA’s products like CFL, Ikea uses 10% recyclable materials and 60% renewable materials. With energy saving, exciting new designs, better light quality, lower environmental impact and 20 years of life, the new LED light is much better than the old incandescent lighting. We changed our entire lighting range into LEDs. This means everything, from bright and accurate kitchen lighting to warm and cozy bedroom lighting. We have an LED lamp for

all your existing lighting installations. Welcome to a new version of lighting, a bright LED world.

We have set of questions:

- Question 1 - Do Green technology products help in achieving the sustainable development?
- Question 2 - Is normal made-up products better then Green technology based products?
- Question 3 - How efficient is the LED lights better than Normal Bulbs?
- Question 4 - Is sustainable development necessary? How important are Green products in achieving sustainable development?
- Question 5 - Have you ever used Ikea's products;do you believe IKEA 's product help in achieving sustainable development?

IX. CONCLUSION

At the start of this investigation, we wondered if IKEA's operations were environmentally friendly. We investigated eco-efficiency as a component of sustainable development and examined various definitions of the term.

"Eco-efficiency is achieved by delivering competitively priced goods," according to the WBCSD, and services that meet human needs and improve life quality while gradually lowering cost ecological impacts and resource intensity must be kept to a minimum throughout the life-cycle. with the earth's estimated carrying capacity" (WBCSD, 2000), i.e. creating more value with fewer resources.

The environmental consequences. WBCSD's proposed formula for calculating eco-efficiency was put to use We calculated the eco-efficiency indicators of IKEA's entire operation to trace the dynamics and the ratios of Ikea’s eco-efficiency.

Our research was used to investigate a positive trend in the use of material resources and CO2 emissions. IKEA succeeded to enhance net sales of items sold per unit of material consumed as well as each unit of product sold CO2 emission unit We, on the other hand, characterized the drop in net sales of things sold per one as a unit of energy spent, i.e. fewer things created per MWh As a result, IKEA's operations, in general, in general, demonstrate a positive eco-efficiency dynamic.

Green Products has a Great significance in sustainable development, Out of 50 people, the data says that , people strongly suggests that Green Products has better efficiency and better life then the normal products. Ikea is making products 10% recyclable materials and 60% renewable materials, so they it creates a deep impact on sustainable development. As per our conclusion, from the questionnaire, it speaks that 35 people strongly agree to the fact that “Have you ever used Ikea's products; do you believe IKEA 's product help in achieving sustainable development?”.

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